

A similarity function on a data set with nominal attributes

Burkhard Möller

August 18, 2022

Abstract: A similarity function on a data set M with nominal attributes is developed and used to determine a classification predictive model.

For $n \in \mathbb{N}$ let $A_1, \dots, A_n$ be nominal attribute value sets where $A_j \neq \emptyset$ for all j , and $T \neq \emptyset$ the target category values.

Let $A := \mathbb{N} \times A_1 \times \dots \times A_n \times T$

Let $k \in \mathbb{N}, k \geq 2$. For all $i \in \{1, \dots, k\}, j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ let $x_{i_0} := i$ and $x_{i_j} \in A_j$ and $x_{i_{n+1}} \in T$, and $x_i := (x_{i_0}, x_{i_1}, \dots, x_{i_n}, x_{i_{n+1}}) \in A$.

Then: x_i belongs to target category $x_{i_{n+1}}$.

Let $M := \{x_1, \dots, x_k\} \subseteq A$ be a data set.

For every $j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ define a function d_j from $M \times A$ to the power set of A_j , i.e.

$$d_j : M \times A \rightarrow P(A_j)$$
$$(x_r, x_s) \mapsto \begin{cases} \{x_{r_j}\} & : \text{if } x_{r_j} = x_{s_j} \\ A_j & : \text{if } x_{r_j} \neq x_{s_j} \end{cases}$$

For all $x_r \in M, x_s \in A, j \in \{1, \dots, n\}$ define

$$M_j : M \times A \rightarrow P(M)$$
$$(x_r, x_s) \mapsto \{x_t \in M \mid x_{t_j} \in d_j(x_r, x_s)\}$$

Definition 1 (similarity extension).

For $x_r \in M, x_s \in A$,

$$M(x_r, x_s) := \bigcap_{j=1}^n M_j(x_r, x_s)$$

is the similarity extension of x_r and x_s in M

Definition 2 (similarity diameter).

For $x_r \in M, x_s \in A$,

$$d_M(x_r, x_s) := |M(x_r, x_s)|$$

is the similarity diameter of x_r and x_s in M

Lemma 1. For $x_r \in M, x_s \in A : d_M(x_r, x_s) \geq 1$

Proof.

Let $x_r \in M, x_s \in A$

$$\Rightarrow \forall j \in \{1, \dots, n\} : d_j(x_r, x_s) \supseteq \{x_{r_j}\}$$

$$\Rightarrow \forall j \in \{1, \dots, n\} : M_j(x_r, x_s) \supseteq \{x_r\}$$

$$\Rightarrow M(x_r, x_s) \supseteq \{x_r\}$$

$$\Rightarrow d_M(x_r, x_s) \geq 1$$

■

Lemma 2. For $x_r \in M, x_s \in M : d_M(x_r, x_s) = d_M(x_s, x_r)$

Proof.

Let $x_r \in M, x_s \in M$

$$\begin{aligned} &\Rightarrow \forall j \in \{1, \dots, n\} : d_j(x_r, x_s) = d_j(x_s, x_r) \\ &\Rightarrow \forall j \in \{1, \dots, n\} : M_j(x_r, x_s) = M_j(x_s, x_r) \\ &\Rightarrow M(x_r, x_s) = M(x_s, x_r) \\ &\Rightarrow d_M(x_r, x_s) = d_M(x_s, x_r) \end{aligned}$$

■

Definition 3 (M-similarity).

For $x_r \in M, x_s \in A$,

$$c_M(x_r, x_s) := \frac{1}{d_M(x_r, x_s)}$$

is the M-similarity of x_r and x_s

Let $T = \{t_1, \dots, t_f\}$ be the target category values.

For each $t_l \in T, x_i = \{x_{i_0}, \dots, x_{i_{n+1}}\} \in M$ define a function

$$\begin{aligned} \varphi_{t_l} : M &\rightarrow \{0, 1\} \\ x_i &\mapsto \begin{cases} 1 & : \text{if } x_{i_{n+1}} = t_l \text{ (i.e. } x_i \text{ belongs to target category } t_l) \\ 0 & : \text{else} \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

Classification of a data point x_q :

Let $x_q := (x_{q_0}, x_{q_1}, \dots, x_{q_n}, x_{q_{n+1}}) \in A$

Let

$$p_{\text{sum}}(x_q) := \sum_{i=1}^k c_M(x_i, x_q)$$

For $t_l \in T$ let

$$p_{t_l \text{sum}}(x_q) := \sum_{i=1}^k \varphi_{t_l}(x_i) \cdot c_M(x_i, x_q)$$

Definition 4 (predicted probability).

For $x_q \in A$, $t_l \in T$

$$p_{t_l}(x_q) := \frac{p_{t_l \text{sum}}(x_q)}{p_{\text{sum}}(x_q)}$$

is the predicted probability of x_q belonging to target category t_l .

Example:

$$\begin{aligned}
A_1 &= \{a, c, g\}, A_2 = \{b, d, f, h\}, A_3 = \{X, Y\}, T = \{s_0, s_1\}, \\
x_1 &= (1, a, b, X, s_1), x_2 = (2, a, d, Y, s_1), x_3 = (3, g, h, Y, s_0), \\
x_4 &= (4, a, f, X, s_1), x_5 = (5, c, d, X, s_0), \\
M &= \{x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5\}
\end{aligned}$$

$\underline{c_M(x_1, x_1)}$:

$$\begin{aligned}
M_1(x_1, x_1) &= \{a\} \Rightarrow M_1(x_1, x_1) = \{x_1, x_2, x_4\} \\
M_2(x_1, x_1) &= \{b\} \Rightarrow M_2(x_1, x_1) = \{x_1\} \\
M_3(x_1, x_1) &= \{X\} \Rightarrow M_3(x_1, x_1) = \{x_1, x_4, x_5\}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\Rightarrow M(x_1, x_1) = M_1(x_1, x_1) \cap M_2(x_1, x_1) \cap M_3(x_1, x_1) = \{x_1\} \\
&\Rightarrow d_M(x_1, x_1) = |M(x_1, x_1)| = 1 \\
&\Rightarrow c_M(x_1, x_1) = \frac{1}{d_M(x_1, x_1)} = 1
\end{aligned}$$

$\underline{c_M(x_1, x_2)}$:

$$\begin{aligned}
M_1(x_1, x_2) &= \{a\} \Rightarrow M_1(x_1, x_2) = \{x_1, x_2, x_4\} \\
M_2(x_1, x_2) &= M_2 = \{b, d, f, h\} \Rightarrow M_2(x_1, x_2) = \{x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5\} \\
M_3(x_1, x_2) &= M_3 = \{X, Y\} \Rightarrow M_3(x_1, x_2) = \{x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5\}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\Rightarrow M(x_1, x_2) = M_1(x_1, x_2) \cap M_2(x_1, x_2) \cap M_3(x_1, x_2) = \{x_1, x_2, x_4\} \\
&\Rightarrow d_M(x_1, x_2) = |M(x_1, x_2)| = 3 \\
&\Rightarrow c_M(x_1, x_2) = \frac{1}{d_M(x_1, x_2)} = \frac{1}{3}
\end{aligned}$$

and in the same way:

$$\begin{aligned}
d_M(x_1, x_3) &= 5 \Rightarrow c_M(x_1, x_3) = \frac{1}{5} \\
d_M(x_1, x_4) &= 2 \Rightarrow c_M(x_1, x_4) = \frac{1}{2} \\
d_M(x_1, x_5) &= 3 \Rightarrow c_M(x_1, x_5) = \frac{1}{3}
\end{aligned}$$

We also have:

$$(\varphi_{s_0}(x_1), \varphi_{s_0}(x_2), \varphi_{s_0}(x_3), \varphi_{s_0}(x_4), \varphi_{s_0}(x_5)) = (0, 0, 1, 0, 1)$$

$$(\varphi_{s_1}(x_1), \varphi_{s_1}(x_2), \varphi_{s_1}(x_3), \varphi_{s_1}(x_4), \varphi_{s_1}(x_5)) = (1, 1, 0, 1, 0)$$

$$p_{\text{sum}}(x_1) = 1 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{5} + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{3} = \frac{71}{30}$$

$$p_{s_0 \text{ sum}}(x_1) = 0 \cdot 1 + 0 \cdot \frac{1}{3} + 1 \cdot \frac{1}{5} + 0 \cdot \frac{1}{2} + 1 \cdot \frac{1}{3} = \frac{8}{15}$$

$$\Rightarrow p_{s_0}(x_1) = \frac{p_{s_0 \text{ sum}}(x_1)}{p_{\text{sum}}(x_1)} = \frac{16}{71} \approx 0.225$$

$$p_{s_1 \text{ sum}}(x_1) = 1 \cdot 1 + 1 \cdot \frac{1}{3} + 0 \cdot \frac{1}{5} + 1 \cdot \frac{1}{2} + 0 \cdot \frac{1}{3} = \frac{11}{6}$$

$$\Rightarrow p_{s_1}(x_1) = \frac{p_{s_1 \text{ sum}}(x_1)}{p_{\text{sum}}(x_1)} = \frac{55}{71} \approx 0.775$$

Furthermore we can determine:

$$c_M(x_2, x_1) = \frac{1}{3}, c_M(x_2, x_2) = 1, c_M(x_2, x_3) = \frac{1}{2}, c_M(x_2, x_4) = \frac{1}{3}, c_M(x_2, x_5) = \frac{1}{2}$$

$$\Rightarrow p_{s_0}(x_2) = 0.375, p_{s_1}(x_2) = 0.625$$

$$c_M(x_3, x_1) = \frac{1}{5}, c_M(x_3, x_2) = \frac{1}{2}, c_M(x_3, x_3) = 1, c_M(x_3, x_4) = \frac{1}{5}, c_M(x_3, x_5) = \frac{1}{5}$$

$$\Rightarrow p_{s_0}(x_3) \approx 0.571, p_{s_1}(x_3) \approx 0.429$$

$$c_M(x_4, x_1) = \frac{1}{2}, c_M(x_4, x_2) = \frac{1}{3}, c_M(x_4, x_3) = \frac{1}{5}, c_M(x_4, x_4) = 1, c_M(x_4, x_5) = \frac{1}{3}$$

$$\Rightarrow p_{s_0}(x_4) \approx 0.225, p_{s_1}(x_4) \approx 0.775$$

$$c_M(x_5, x_1) = \frac{1}{3}, c_M(x_5, x_2) = \frac{1}{2}, c_M(x_5, x_3) = \frac{1}{5}, c_M(x_5, x_4) = \frac{1}{3}, c_M(x_5, x_5) = 1$$

$$\Rightarrow p_{s_0}(x_5) \approx 0.507, p_{s_1}(x_5) \approx 0.493$$

Let $x_6 := (x_{6_0}, x_{6_1}, x_{6_2}, x_{6_3}, x_{6_4}) = (6, a, h, Y, x_{6_4})$ be a new data point with (possibly unknown) target category x_{6_4} .

We get

$$M(x_1, x_6) = \{x_1, x_2, x_4\} \Rightarrow d_M(x_1, x_6) = 3 \Rightarrow c_M(x_1, x_6) = \frac{1}{3}$$

$$M(x_2, x_6) = \{x_2\} \Rightarrow d_M(x_2, x_6) = 1 \Rightarrow c_M(x_2, x_6) = 1$$

$$M(x_3, x_6) = \{x_3\} \Rightarrow d_M(x_3, x_6) = 1 \Rightarrow c_M(x_3, x_6) = 1$$

$$M(x_4, x_6) = \{x_1, x_2, x_4\} \Rightarrow d_M(x_4, x_6) = 3 \Rightarrow c_M(x_4, x_6) = \frac{1}{3}$$

$$M(x_5, x_6) = \{x_1, x_2, x_3, x_4, x_5\} \Rightarrow d_M(x_5, x_6) = 5 \Rightarrow c_M(x_5, x_6) = \frac{1}{5}$$

$$p_{\text{sum}}(x_6) = \frac{1}{3} + 1 + 1 + \frac{1}{3} + \frac{1}{5} = \frac{43}{15}$$

$$p_{s_0 \text{ sum}}(x_6) = 0 \cdot \frac{1}{3} + 0 \cdot 1 + 1 \cdot 1 + 0 \cdot \frac{1}{3} + 1 \cdot \frac{1}{5} = \frac{6}{5}$$

$$\Rightarrow p_{s_0}(x_6) = \frac{p_{s_0 \text{ sum}}(x_6)}{p_{\text{sum}}(x_6)} = \frac{18}{43} \approx 0.419$$

$$p_{s_1 \text{ sum}}(x_6) = 1 \cdot \frac{1}{3} + 1 \cdot 1 + 0 \cdot 1 + 1 \cdot \frac{1}{3} + 0 \cdot \frac{1}{5} = \frac{5}{3}$$

$$\Rightarrow p_{s_1}(x_6) = \frac{p_{s_1 \text{ sum}}(x_6)}{p_{\text{sum}}(x_6)} = \frac{25}{43} \approx 0.581$$

So x_6 belongs to target category s_0 with a predicted probability of 0.419 and to target category s_1 with a predicted probability of 0.581.